

VERY HIGH FREQUENCY INDUCED FATIGUE DAMAGE

Stanislava FINTOVÁ¹, Ivo KUBĚNA¹, Alice CHLUPOVÁ¹, Ivo ŠULÁK¹, Zdeněk CHLUP¹, Libor TRŠKO², Jaroslav POLÁK¹

¹ Institute of Physics of Materials Czech Academy of Sciences, Žitkova 513/22, 616 00 Brno, Czech Republic

² Research Centre of the University of Žilina, Univerzitná 8215/1, 010 26 Žilina, Slovak Republic

Contact: fintova@ipm.cz

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10797709

Keywords: very high cycle fatigue, very high-frequency loading, steel, fatigue damage, FIB tomography, cavities

Abstract

Fatigue lifetime and fatigue endurance limit are for many materials enhanced due to the increased strain rate. As a consequence of the strain rate sensitivity, ultrasonic fatigue testing yields S-N curve well above the conventionally obtained ones, while material strengthening was observed only in some cases. Thus, the understanding of the fatigue damage mechanisms operating under very high frequencies and their relation to the conventional testing results is crucial for the lifetime prediction in the very high cycle fatigue region.

Fatigue life and the fatigue endurance limit of the ferritic-pearlitic structure steel were enhanced with the increase in test frequency from 20 Hz to 20 kHz. On the other hand, the character of the created surface relief was similar for all the test conditions, in terms of test frequency and stress amplitude applied. The increased testing frequency reduced the number of slip markings, nevertheless, it seems that test frequency had only a slight impact on the height/depth of the extrusions/intrusions. Focused ion beam tomography and 3D reconstruction of the volume below the slip markings demonstrated the cavity distribution within the material volume and along the slip plane. No slip markings were observed in the pearlite areas. Fatigue crack initiation took place predominantly in the slip markings, however, subsurface cavity-assisted crack initiation was occasionally observed too. Coalescence of cavities along the slip plane facilitated the fatigue crack initiation and early growth. No difference in damage mechanism was detected regardless of the testing frequency or stress amplitude.

Introduction

Fatigue crack initiation is an important period of the fatigue life. Thus, understanding the mechanism of the fatigue crack initiation is crucial for the prediction of the fatigue life and design procedures. However, since the demands on the safety and economic aspects of the industry are still increasing, the requirements on the materials' properties are increasing as well. As a response, new materials with enhanced properties are developed and new testing and production technologies are invented. One of the commonly used methods today is to increase the loading frequency. The increased loading frequency should correspond to the high-frequency loading applied in real applications and/or the necessity to reach the required number of cycles (usually above 10^8 cycles) in a relevant time [1]. Several studies were published analyzing the impact of the test frequency on material response to the fatigue loading and the resulting fatigue lifetime [2-14]. On the other hand, except for relevant attempts, the fatigue

crack initiation mechanism under ultrasonic loading is not explained sufficiently till now even for common structural materials.

A commonly accepted approach for fatigue crack initiation is the vacancy model [15] explaining the localization of the cyclic plastic deformation into persistent slip bands (PSBs) parallel to the primary slip plane that produce persistent slip markings (PSMs) on the surface. According to the model, vacancies are steadily produced both in the channels and the walls of the ladder-like PSB structure and migrate to the matrix. Both extrusions and intrusions develop on the surface until cracks start from intrusions. This approach is very well adopted for the low cycle fatigue region and is accepted also for the high cycle fatigue region, while its applicability into the very high cycle fatigue region, usually approachable only by ultrasonic frequencies represents an open question for many materials.

Steels remain to be commonly and widely used materials. A lot of experimental data can be found and the fatigue damage mechanism was described for many steels, however, mostly only for the low and high cycle fatigue region. Some authors provided data for the very high cycle fatigue region, nevertheless, data are usually not accompanied by data obtained under conventional test conditions [4, 5, 13, 16, 17]. On the other hand, even in the case, where the tests were performed with several frequencies, the authors' attention was not focused on the comparison of the mechanisms acting under different frequencies. Considering the other test conditions constant they provided only the fatigue life data except for some studies with partial fractographic and structural investigations [9-11, 13]. Most high-strength steels are tested because of their potential use in the practice. For most of them, the fatigue crack initiates on the surface defects at high-stress amplitudes or on the subsurface defects or internal inclusions for low-stress amplitudes [9, 13, 17]. Fintová et al. [9] compared the fatigue properties of EA4T railway axle steel with martensitic structure when tested under conventional 120 Hz and ultrasonic 20 kHz. As usual, the increased test frequency shifted the lifetime to a higher number of cycles to fracture, even though the fracture mechanism remained unchanged. The fatigue endurance limit was to be the same for both test frequencies.

However, this is not the case for materials with lower strength properties and higher plasticity, usually containing a lower amount of carbon. Plastic deformation concentrates in the soft phase, namely in the PSMs that act as the crack initiation sites. However, in the presence of the inclusions, the internal metallic or/and non-metallic inclusions act as stress concentrators and initiate the crack in ultrasonic testing [12, 16].

The sensitivity to the loading frequency was shown to be an issue for the low carbon steel by Guennec et al. in [10, 11] tested at various frequencies (from 0.2 Hz to 20 kHz). The increase of the test frequency from 0.2 to 140 Hz resulted in the shift of the S-N curve to the higher number of cycles to the fracture and to the increase in the fatigue endurance limit for the material with the ferritic-pearlitic structure. An additional increase of the test frequency to 20 kHz resulted in a dramatic increase in the lifetime and fatigue endurance limit. The test frequency change from the conventional to the ultrasonic was shown to have an impact on the dislocation structure changing it from ladder-like or cells to long segments of screw dislocations without clear walls, respectively [10]. Also, the change in the fatigue crack initiation mechanism was caused by the change in the test frequency. The test frequencies from 0.2 to 140 Hz were characterized by the crack initiation from PSMs arising in the ferritic grains, while the intergranular crack initiation occurred at 20 kHz [10]. Authors tried to explain the gap between the S-N curves obtained under conventional and ultrasonic frequency via micro-plasticity behavior such as the stress-strain hysteresis loop and the local misorientation [11]. Only a slight difference in misorientation was revealed by EBSD for the tests performed at 20 Hz and 140 Hz which was explained by the authors via material softening. However, a significant decrease in the local misorientation was found after loading at 20 kHz. Authors

concluded, that some other potential factors, in addition to the strain rate effect on the yield stress, should be taken into consideration under ultrasonic loading conditions [11].

When no defects or inclusions were present in the material its plasticity allowed the formation of PSMs, formation of PSMs, and nucleation of cavities along the PSMs in the ferrite phase at ultrasonic frequency [12]. Diffusion of vacancies due to high temperature under ultrasonic fatigue loading was proposed by the authors to be the main cause of cavities formation as it was not observed under low-frequency loading. In the low and high cycle fatigue regimes, the fatigue crack initiation on the SMs was observed.

A previous study by the authors performed on pure copper [2] focused on the mechanism of the fatigue crack initiation under ultrasonic loading and showed a similar response of the material to the loading regardless of the test frequency. Focused ion beam (FIB) tomography and 3D visualization of the fatigue damage in combination with transmission electron microscopy (TEM) observations of site-specific samples revealed the internal damage. Vacancies produced below the PSMs along the primary slip planes were observed to coalesce and result in crack formation. The mechanism was the same for all the test frequencies and only the kinetics of the process changed due to the strain rate dependence.

The presented paper deals with the influence of testing frequency on fatigue properties. A thorough microstructural analysis was performed to explain the differences in the fatigue behavior. The presence of cyclic plastic deformation was represented by slip markings where the slip bands intersected the sample surface. The occurrence of slip markings slightly varied with the stress amplitude and frequency, but the damaging mechanism remained the same in all investigated samples. The difference is discussed in terms of the dislocation and vacation motion kinetics.

Experimental material and procedures

Experimental material and structural analysis

A C15E ferritic-pearlitic steel was examined to establish the influence of the loading frequency on the fatigue damage evolution and its character. Table 1 provides a chemical composition of the examined steel determined by the optical emission spectroscope SPECTROMAXx. The material was delivered in the form of rolled bars.

Table 1 Chemical composition of the examined steel (wt. %).

C	Mn	Si	P	S	Cr	Ni
0.149±0.008	0.369±0.003	0.0238±0.006	0.011±0.001	0.017±0.002	0.089±0.004	0.015±0.002
Cu	Al	W	Mo	V	other	Fe
0.023±0.001	0.043±0.005	-	0.004±0.001	0.004±0.001		98.975±0.050

The microstructure of the examined material was analyzed on the samples prepared from the cuts performed parallelly and perpendicularly to the rolled bars axes. Metallographically prepared samples were etched by the Nital solution. Basic microstructural analysis was performed using Olympus GX51 inverted metallographic light optical microscope (LM). A Tescan LYRA 3 XMU FEG/SEMxFIB scanning electron microscope (SEM) was used to examine the individual microstructural features in sections parallel and perpendicular to the rolling direction including the grain size determination when the electron backscattered diffraction (EBSD) technique was applied.

The focused ion beam (FIB) technique, adopting the gas injection system (GIS) for the coverage of the inspected surface by Pt, was used to perform the cuts to reveal the subsurface structure and internal damage evolution cumulated within the material due to the fatigue loading. The internal structure of the material was analyzed using Talos F200i transmission electron microscope (TEM). In the case of the basic material, the dislocation density and arrangement

were studied on conventionally prepared foils (grinding and electrolytic polishing). The evolution of the structure was analyzed on the site-specific lamellas extracted from the slip markings using FIB. The FIB lamellas were extracted in the direction perpendicular to the SM created on the sample surface while the created relief was covered by Pt before FIB milling to protect the character of the extrusion/intrusion and eventually the crack initiation.

The microstructure of the material consists of polyhedral grains of ferrite with islands of pearlite. Fig. 1 shows the microstructure in the longitudinal direction (parallel to the delivered bars rolling direction). LM allowed to determine the area fraction of the ferrite and pearlite, which was $85.2 \pm 1.0\%$ to $11.5 \pm 1.4\%$ for the perpendicular cut and $86.9 \pm 0.8\%$ to $12.9 \pm 0.8\%$ for the parallel cut. Grain size as well as the orientation distribution function (ODF) were determined based on three different areas with a size of $375 \times 500 \mu\text{m}$. The grain size determined based on EBSD maps is $(10.9 \pm 6.3) \mu\text{m}$ in transversal and $(13.4 \pm 8.8) \mu\text{m}$ in longitudinal direction. The structure exhibited preferential grain orientation in the rolling direction (Fig. 1d). The maximal value of ODF was 4.03 indicating mild texture in $\langle 111 \rangle$ direction. Individual dislocations were observed in the ferritic grains (Fig. 1e) as well as in the ferritic areas between the cementite lamellae in the pearlite regions of the structure (Fig. 1f). No specific dislocation arrangement was observed in the basic material before cycling.

Fig. 1 Microstructure of the examined steel in the longitudinal direction.

Tensile tests

To analyze the strain rate sensitivity of the material two types of tensile tests were performed; conventional (quasi-static) and high-speed (dynamic). The tests were run in the laboratory air at a laboratory temperature of $(23 \pm 2) ^\circ\text{C}$. A universal Zwick Roell Z50 screw-driven testing machine was used for the quasi-static tensile tests. The crosshead speed was set to correspond to the average strain rates of 0.0005 s^{-1} , 0.0286 s^{-1} , and 0.2857 s^{-1} . The strain was precisely

measured with an extensometer. An Amsler RKP 300 instrumented impact pendulum with additional weight equipped with an instrumented tensile jig was used for the dynamic tensile tests. The release angle was set to reach the initial impact speed corresponding to the strain rates of 53.50 s^{-1} , 77.81 s^{-1} , and 149.84 s^{-1} .

Tensile properties of the material at different strain rates were characterized by the proof stress obtained at 0.2 % of plastic deformation (PS), ultimate tensile strength (UTS), and total elongation (ductility, A). The elongation was calculated using the primary gauge length of the specimen. The values of PS and UTS were determined from the records of the dynamic tensile tests by fitting the data by a suitable spline to eliminate the inertia effects in the case of dynamic tests. Specimens of the same geometry (see Fig. 2a) were used for both tests. Several tensile tests were performed at each strain rate and a good reproducibility has been achieved.

Fatigue tests

Conventional and very high-frequency fatigue tests were performed to elucidate the influence of the testing frequency on the fatigue damage mechanism in the case of C15E ferritic-pearlitic steel. Conventional fatigue tests were performed at a frequency of 20 Hz using an Instron E3000 electrodynamic testing instrument with linear motor technology. Samples were tested under the load control mode in a symmetrical tension-compression sinusoidal waveform ($R = -1$) in the laboratory air and temperature of $(23 \pm 2) \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

A piezoelectric ultrasonic system made by Lasur® tuned in to the frequency of 20 kHz was used for the very high-frequency tests. To prevent the tested sample heating, the closed circuit of the deionized water-cooling system was adopted. The samples were tested by controlling the displacement (i.e. the total strain amplitude), however, due to negligible plastic strain amplitude the loading conditions can be considered to be equivalent to a stress-controlled mode. A specific sample geometry (see Fig. 2b) had to be proposed and adjusted to reach the resonance frequency of the system.

An identical sample geometry was used for the conventional and the very high-frequency fatigue tests. Before the testing, the surface of the samples was mechanically ground using SiC papers, polished using the diamond paste under ethanol as a lubricant, and finally chemically mechanically polished using colloidal silica suspension to facilitate observation of the surface relief generated during fatigue loading.

Fig. 2 Geometry of the test samples. Dimensions are in mm.

To determine the fatigue endurance limit, at least three runout samples on the same stress amplitude were tested. Runouts were considered the samples that exceeded the 10^7 cycles and 10^{10} cycles for frequencies 20 Hz and 20 kHz, respectively.

Fatigue damage analysis

The evolution of the surface relief due to the localization of the cyclic plastic deformation during cycling on the tested samples' surface was observed by SEM. Several locations on the surface with PSMs were chosen for cutting by FIB to elucidate the evolution of the surface relief and fatigue crack initiation. The FIB cuts were performed in the direction perpendicular

to the PSMs. To get information about the space distribution of the fatigue damage below the PSMs, FIB tomography was adopted. The PSMs and the surrounding area were covered by Pt ($20 \times 15 \mu\text{m}$) to protect the created relief. A trench having a height/depth of about $20 \mu\text{m}$ was produced using FIB milling. The material was sliced with a thickness of 100 nm perpendicular to the surface and the direction of the PSM. After each slice, the SEM image of the respective cut was taken. ImageJ software was used for the image processing and the AVIZO software was adopted for the 3D reconstruction of the resulting damage below the PSMs. For more details see [2].

FIB was also used to extract the site-specific TEM lamellae from the tested samples. The TEM lamellae were extracted perpendicularly to the PSMs, covering the PSMs surface by Pt before the procedure.

A low acceleration voltage of 2 kV was used for the final lamellae polishing to minimize the gallium ions damage.

Results

Mechanical properties

The results of the tensile tests performed on the ferritic-pearlitic steel showing its strain rate sensitivity are presented in Fig. 3. Typical increase of the flow stress with strain rate is demonstrated. As can be seen in Fig. 3a and 3b, PS and UTS increase considerably with the strain rate while only a slight increase in the case of A is seen. The change of the tensile test, from the quasi-static to the dynamic, resulted in a steep increase of the PS and UTS, while the change of A was again only minor.

The dependence of the fatigue strength on the cycling frequency is apparent from the fatigue tests, see Fig. 3c. The S-N curve obtained at 20 kHz was shifted to the longer fatigue life when compared to the lower test frequency approximately by two orders of magnitude. Some scatter of experimental data can be seen for the samples tested at 20 kHz at low-stress amplitudes (considering the test conditions equal to the stress control mode). Nevertheless, the fatigue endurance limit determined for 20 kHz was higher, compared to the one determined for 20 Hz , 297 MPa , and 261 MPa , respectively.

For all the stress amplitudes, the principal fatigue crack initiated from the surface. No inclusions or other defects were observed by SEM in the crack origin area. As discussed in an earlier paper [2], the strain rate during cycling is proportional to the frequency. We can deduce that the shift of the fatigue life curve to the higher stress amplitude is due to an increase in the strain rate.

a) quasi-static and dynamic tensile test

b) change of the tensile characteristics with the strain rate

c) S-N curves of the experimental steel obtained at two test frequencies. Broken samples are represented by full symbols and runout samples are represented by empty symbols.

Fig. 3 Mechanical properties of the examined material.

Fatigue damage analysis – FIB cutting and TEM

Inspection of the surface of the tested samples revealed a large number of PSMs created during cycling. Under the loading conditions, the PSMs evolution was the most notable in the central part of the samples, and with the increasing distance from the central part with the narrowest diameter, the number of PSMs decreased. No correlation between the size (heights or lengths) of the PSMs and distance from the central part of the individual samples or the stress amplitude was observed. Separated PSMs or PSMs families were observed in individual grains, while all the time, only the ferritic grains were producing PSMs.

FIB cuts performed perpendicular to PSMs on samples tested at various stress amplitudes revealed the fatigue damage within the material. The images of the FIB cuts are shown in Fig. 4. Extrusions and intrusions on the material surface were accompanied by damage in the form of cavities and surface cracks. The cracks were present in the majority of cuts. The cracks appear simultaneously with the intrusions. It indicates the cracks start from intrusions. However, cavities present below the PSMs and their coalescence also affect the initiation and growth.

When analyzing the broken samples, FIB cuts were performed on PSMs at a distance of at least 1 mm from the fracture surface to prevent any effect of the plastic zone on the analyzed area during the propagation of the crack responsible for the sample failure. No specific difference was observed between the surface features of the samples broken during the test and runout samples.

Fig. 4 FIB cuts performed on samples tested at different frequencies. The surface of the samples was covered by Pt before FIB cutting. The loading direction is marked by an arrow at each insert showing the cut SMs.

TEM analysis of the lamellae extracted from the tested samples allowed detailed observation of the changes in the internal structure induced by fatigue. In the lamellae taken from the sample cycled at 20 Hz (Fig. 5a), the PSB running parallel to the primary slip plane shows a dislocation arrangement corresponding to alternating dislocation walls and channels. This corresponds to the case of polycrystalline copper [18]. Due to the localization of the cyclic plastic deformation the presence of cavities, even in the nanoscale, along the trace of the primary slip plane was detected.

The lamellae prepared from the sample cycled at 20 kHz (see Fig 5b) reveal the extrusion and a small parallel intrusion but no special dislocation arrangement is apparent in a specific crystallographic direction. Nanoscale cavities can be observed along the trace of the primary slip plane.

a) 20 Hz, 261 MPa, $N = 1 \times 10^7$ cycles b) 20 kHz, 298 MPa, $N = 1 \times 10^{10}$ cycles
 Fig. 5. TEM analysis of runout samples. The trace of the primary slip plane is marked by a dashed lines and the cavities are marked by arrows.

FIB slicing and 3D visualization

To visualize the distribution of the fatigue damage below the PSMs the FIB slicing and 3D reconstruction have been performed. Reconstruction of the individual slices reveals the distribution of cavities in the neighborhood of individual crystal planes (presumably slip planes) (Fig. 6a). Even though only one PSM is present on the sample surface, the FIB slicing reveals a batch of cavities below the sample surface scattered along a slip plane below the PSMs. A family of PSMs in the sample tested at 20 kHz is shown in Fig. 6b. Only a section containing the two largest PSMs is displayed in 3D image. All the PSMs are present in one grain, the cavities are distributed along one slip plane as seen in the 3D visualization.

a) 20 Hz, 261 MPa, $N = 1 \times 10^7$ cycles, runout
 b) 20 kHz, 298 MPa, $N = 1 \times 10^{10}$ cycles, runout
 Fig. 6 3D reconstruction of fatigue damage just below the SMs – cavities distribution. The loading direction and the slicing direction are marked by a white and a black arrow, respectively. SMs were localized on the top of the 3D block.

Discussion

Cyclic loading of ferritic-pearlitic steel with constant stress amplitudes and two frequencies showed a strong dependence of the fatigue life curve on the frequency. A similar strong dependence of the cyclic stress amplitude on the frequency (up to 20kHz) has been found by Torabian et al. [12] and Guennec et al. [11]. To explain the substantial increase of the stress amplitude the tensile testing with different strain rates was performed. The monotonic tensile curves show a similar dependence on the strain rate as the stress amplitude. With the increase in frequency from 20 Hz to 20 kHz (1000 times) the stress amplitude increased to around 130%. In tensile tests, the same increase in the strain rate led (on average) to the increase of the yield stress to about the same value. This indicates that strain rate is responsible for the shift of the fatigue life curve to the higher stresses or higher fatigue lives in agreement with previous observations on polycrystalline copper [2].

Observations of the surface evolution in cyclic straining showed that persistent slip markings develop only in the ferritic grains which agrees with the higher strength of the pearlite. No difference was found in the character of the fatigue damage evolved in cycling with two frequencies. Not only surface observations but also FIB cuts in locations of PSMs showed a similar picture of the surface damage leading to the initiation of the fatigue cracks. Small extrusions, often accompanied by intrusions and in the bulk either a tiny crack and/or small cavities. This indicates the simultaneous development of extrusions/intrusions and cavities. The cracks start from intrusions and their growth is affected by the presence of cavities.

Selected foils prepared from the surface of the sample (Fig. 5) showed a dislocation structure below PSM. A band parallel to the trace of the primary slip plane corresponds to the PSB found in f.c.c. metals. Only a short section of the band was imaged in Fig. 5a. Its dislocation structure cannot be characterized as ladder-like, nevertheless alternating dislocation walls and channels can be identified. This corresponds to a structure that can produce vacancies in the channels. Vacancies can partially migrate to the surrounding matrix and atoms wander in the opposite direction, i.e. in the PSB. This mechanism leads to the formation of extrusions and intrusions [15]. The image of the foil taken from the runout sample cycled with 20 kHz shows an extrusion but the dislocation structure was not identified. Numerous cavities are present in the PSB and close to it.

FIB slicing of the material perpendicular to the PSMs yields 3D visualization of cavities below individual PSM (Fig. 6a) or below the selected area of the PSM group (Fig. 6b). In both cases samples were subjected to a high number of cycles (runout samples) but no crack has developed. Nevertheless, the damage in both cases starts developing in the form of a high density of small cavities below PSMs. The cavities are arranged along the line corresponding to the trace of the primary slip plane. The highest density of the cavities was close to the surface and reached a depth of around 5 μm . The cavities with lower density were scattered to a depth of up to 15 μm . The presence of the cavities produced in cyclic straining indicates the damage that can contribute to the initiation of a crack by linking the cavities subjected to the varying cyclic shear stress parallel to the primary slip plane.

In the case of higher stress amplitude, the cavities in high-frequency cycling arise too. When the crack starts from an intrusion the cavities along its path facilitate the crack growth by joining to the growing crack.

Until now, no direct evidence has been presented that can disclose the mechanism of cavity formation during cyclic loading. Natural explanation offers the linking of vacancy type of defect produced in cyclic straining [15, 19]. In cycling with a low strain rate, vacancies are produced and simultaneously migrate to edge dislocations contributing to the formation of PSMs. If the strain rate is high and dislocation density in the neighbor matrix is low the probability of vacancy encounter increases and their agglomeration can result in cavity formation. The present results thus indicate the possibility of a new mechanism of fatigue crack initiation in high-

frequency, low-amplitude cyclic loading, namely linking of cavities formed in the PSM along the PSB. This proposal agrees with the observed elementary crack on the surface of polycrystalline copper cycled in very high cycle fatigue [20] and with elementary subsurface cracks in the same material found by Weidner et al. [6].

In some cases, families of cavities were observed in the grains oriented for multiple slip using FIB tomography. These cavities correspond to two slip systems and therefore cracks in two different slip planes can arise simultaneously. Usually, only one slip system is more effective than the other and the growth of secondary crack is suppressed.

Conclusions

The investigation of the evolution of the fatigue damage in the ferrite-pearlite structure of C15E steel due to the cyclic loading and its dependence on the loading frequency led to the following conclusions:

- The material exhibits strain rate sensitivity in the case of static as well as dynamic tests. Tensile strength properties increased dramatically with increased strain rate, while the increase of elongation was only minor. The S-N curve was shifted to the higher stress amplitude or the higher number of cycles when the test frequency was increased from 20 Hz to 20 kHz. The fatigue endurance limit increased from 297 MPa to 261 MPa.
- TEM study affirmed the low height of extrusions and the presence of specific dislocation structure below the PSM with many cavities in the PSB.
- FIB cuts revealed 3D distribution of cavities below PSMs around the trace of the crystallographic slip plane. Their origin, coalescence, and role in the formation of fatigue cracks were discussed.
- No significant difference between the fatigue damage mechanism in samples tested with low and high frequency was observed. The strain rate effect was found responsible for the increase of the stress amplitude and/or fatigue life in testing with the ultrasonic frequency.

Acknowledgement

This publication was supported by the project "Mechanical Engineering of Biological and Bio-inspired Systems", funded as project No. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004634 by Programme Johannes Amos Comenius, call Excellent Research.

Data availability

Data are available at [10.5281/zenodo.10782242](https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10782242).

References

- [1] L. Trško, F. Nový, O. Bokůvka, M. Jambor, Ultrasonic Fatigue Testing in the Tension-Compression Mode. LID - 10.3791/57007 [doi] LID - 57007.
- [2] S. Fintová, I. Kuběna, A. Chlupová, M. Jambor, I. Šulák, Z. Chlup, J. Polák, Frequency-dependent fatigue damage in polycrystalline copper analyzed by FIB tomography, *Acta Materialia*, 211 (2021) 116859.
- [3] S. Fintová, I. Kuběna, L. Trško, V. Horník, L. Kunz, Fatigue behavior of AW7075 aluminum alloy in ultra-high cycle fatigue region, *Materials Science and Engineering: A*, 774 (2020) 138922.
- [4] J. Klusák, S. Fintová, K. Kozáková, M. Jambor, S. Seitzl, Risk volume effect in very high cycle fatigue of 304L stainless steel, *International Journal of Fatigue*, 178 (2024) 108016.

- [5] K. Kozáková, J. Klusák, S. Fintová, The length parameter for gigacycle fatigue life predictions of notched specimens made of 304L steel, *International Journal of Fatigue*, 178 (2024) 107980.
- [6] A. Weidner, D. Amberger, F. Pyczak, B. Schönbauer, S. Stanzl-Tschegg, H. Mughrabi, Fatigue damage in copper polycrystals subjected to ultrahigh-cycle fatigue below the PSB threshold, *International Journal of Fatigue*, 32 (2010) 872-878.
- [7] I. Marines, X. Bin, C. Bathias, An understanding of very high cycle fatigue of metals, *International Journal of Fatigue*, 25 (2003) 1101-1107.
- [8] Q.Y. Wang, J.Y. Berard, A. Dubarre, G. Baudry, S. Rathery, C. Bathias, Gigacycle fatigue of ferrous alloys, *Fatigue & Fracture of Engineering Materials & Structures*, 22 (1999) 667-672.
- [9] S. Fintová, P. Pokorný, R. Fajkoš, P. Hutař, EA4T railway axle steel fatigue behavior under very high-frequency fatigue loading, *Engineering Failure Analysis*, 115 (2020) 104668.
- [10] B. Guennec, A. Ueno, T. Sakai, M. Takanashi, Y. Itabashi, M. Ota, Dislocation-based interpretation on the effect of the loading frequency on the fatigue properties of JIS S15C low carbon steel, *International Journal of Fatigue*, 70 (2015) 328-341.
- [11] B. Guennec, A. Ueno, T. Sakai, M. Takanashi, Y. Itabashi, Effect of the loading frequency on fatigue properties of JIS S15C low carbon steel and some discussions based on micro-plasticity behavior, *International Journal of Fatigue*, 66 (2014) 29-38.
- [12] N. Torabian, V. Favier, J. Dirrenberger, F. Adamski, S. Ziaei-Rad, N. Ranc, Correlation of the high and very high cycle fatigue response of ferrite based steels with strain rate-temperature conditions, *Acta Materialia*, 134 (2017) 40-52.
- [13] A. Sharma, M.C. Oh, B. Ahn, Recent Advances in Very High Cycle Fatigue Behavior of Metals and Alloys—A Review, *Metals*, 10 (2020).
- [14] S. Fintová, L. Trško, Z. Chlup, F. Pastorek, D. Kajánek, L. Kunz, Fatigue Crack Initiation Change of Cast AZ91 Magnesium Alloy from Low to Very High Cycle Fatigue Region, *Materials*, 14 (2021) 6245.
- [15] J. Polák, J. Man, Fatigue crack initiation – The role of point defects, *International Journal of Fatigue*, 65 (2014) 18-27.
- [16] P. Chu, L. Xu, H. Wang, R. An, J. Zhang, Effect of microstructure on gigacycle fatigue and crack growth behavior of X80 grade pipeline steels, *Theoretical and Applied Fracture Mechanics*, 123 (2023) 103704.
- [17] D. Spriestersbach, E. Kerscher, The role of local plasticity during very high cycle fatigue crack initiation in high-strength steels, *International Journal of Fatigue*, 111 (2018) 93-100.
- [18] J. Polák, V. Mazanova, M. Heczko, I. Kuběna, J. Man, Profiles of persistent slip markings and internal structure of underlying persistent slip bands, *Fatigue & Fracture of Engineering Materials & Structures*, 40 (2017).
- [19] J. Polák, Production, annihilation and migration of point defects in cyclic straining, *Materialia*, 14 (2020) 100938.
- [20] S. Stanzl-Tschegg, B. Schönbauer, C. Laird, Mechanisms of fatigue failure of polycrystalline copper in the VHCF-regime, *TMS Annual Meeting*, (2008) 229-234.